

Managing machine learning in times of sudden disruption (COVID-19) in the insurance industry

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ABSTRACT

As organizations struggle to manage the impact of COVID-19 on their operations and supply chains, even greater pressure is placed on insurers to provide support to their clients. Moreover, they have to bear in mind mitigating the downsides for their own business and processes.

Simultaneously, markets are struggling while experiencing catastrophic losses like higher reinsurance costs. Already a long time before COVID-19 outbreak, insurance companies were striving to keep up with increasing asperity and uncertainty of natural disasters, terrorist attacks, epidemics and other risks emerging. Therefore, insurers were looking for the next generation technologies long before COVID-19. Long before industry was in need to compute adequate rates and come up with new premiums, while also thinking of securing their own profitability. However, now it is not prevention anymore, we need to take an action immediately and some models occur not suitable. In order to search for the solution we need to turn to Big Data Analytics.

Deloitte's survey from 2019 (E. Hida, 2018) states that only approximately 40% of organizations utilize big data and make use of big data analytics, despite the fact that over 60% of responders believe the emerging tech could drastically increase operational efficiency and improve risk analysis. Therefore, we need to push to increase those numbers.

Keywords

COVID-19, Insurance Industry, sudden disruption, disruptive events, big data, pandemics, business process integration, IT Governance, Strategic Sourcing, Cybersecurity

INTRODUCTION

This research is about a proposed way of managing big data analytics, and in particular machine learning models, in times of sudden disruption, like COVID-19. The scope extends itself to the insurance industry. The insurance industry has long been relying on machine learning models as support in decision making, price setting, and customer segmentation. However, the data underlying these decision-support models are based on training data from before a disruptive event. Take for instance the outbreak of COVID-19. The COVID-19 outbreak has disrupted the insurance market which resulted in a change of customer data, customer interactions, and customer behaviour. The implication of this research is therefore that the models the insurance industry is relying on are no longer valid. Premium price setting and customer risk profiling on the basis of data from before a disruptive event is incorrect.

Our research is set out not to find a way to optimize machine learning models, but rather to propose a way of dealing with sudden disruptions. The research will go into the aspects of how to govern big data analytics in a world where sudden disruption is possible at any moment. Furthermore, this research ought to gather knowledge on the implications of sudden disruptive events on cybersecurity & risk management. Moreover, the research will provide a sketch of how Business Process Integration may enhance an effective and efficient management process in times of sudden disruption.

RESEARCH

Approach

In order to generate qualitative knowledge, this research will be built on non-experimental, descriptive design, where secondary data will be considered. We will focus on the insurance industry and conduct data archival research as reference collected from other studies and similar efforts. We will not focus on a particular country, age group or other variables, but on the insurance industry only, across the globe.

Furthermore, in order to access data relevant for this paper we will access government statistics, government reports, financial reports of organizations in the industry, sales reports of organizations in the industry, official statistics, government publications, government sponsored sources, academic publications, journals, syndicated data from households and syndicated data on insurance industry. Earlier research on past disruptions will be also revised, in favor of getting a broader perspective on the subject.

FINANCIAL SECTOR

Insurance market

The Dutch Authority for the Financial Markets (AFM) divides the insurance sector into three main types of insurances, which consist of 'life insurance', 'property and casualty insurance' and 'health insurance'. (AFM, 2020) There are 243 non-life insurance companies and 40 life insurance companies following the latest data from the Central Agency for Statistics (CBS) in 2015, but the number of insurers has declined throughout the years. (CBS, 2017)

There are different key players in every type of insurance sector. The key players in the life insurance market are Nationale-Nederlanden, SRLEV, AEGON, Achmea, ASR and Delta Lloyd. Whereas the non-life insurance sector has different top players in terms of market share, which consist of Achmea, ASR, Nationale-Nederlanden, Delta Lloyd and Reaal. And then there is also the health insurance market, which is the most stable one since the biggest four key players in the market have been on the same ranking based on market share since 2008. The four key players of the health insurance market are Achmea, VGZ, CZ and Menzis. They have been very stable due to many mergers and acquisitions and because of the rising number of insurance policies which they offered in the market. (*Competition in the Dutch health insurance*

market, 2016) (*The Dutch insurance market 2017, 2018*)

Despite the fact that there are different types of insurances and different key players, this research is meant for all kinds of insurance companies, so they can improve their machine learning models to withstand sudden disruptions.

Key developments

The insurance sector has gone through some key developments in the years prior to COVID-19. Most of the developments were technology-related, but there were also some general developments in the market. The market mainly improved because of the rise of the 'Insurtechs'. Insurtechs are technology-based companies that entered the insurance sector in recent years. They are taking advantage of the newest technologies to automate processes, increase customer experience and reduce costs. (Catlin et al., 2017)

One of the biggest developments of the industry was the introduction of big data analytics. The usage of big data has provided insurance companies with an increased level of relevant information. They got better insights about customer preferences, behaviors and risk patterns. (Soar, 2015) Due to big data, insurance companies were also able to use diagnostic and predictive analytics to forecast the expected behaviour of policyholders and take actions based on the outcomes. This way, they were able to select their prices based on different risk classifications. (*The Impact of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Insurance Sector*, 2020)

Another development in the market came with artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence has been used to improve and automate customer underwriting- and claims processes. It enables insurers to access data faster, decrease human labor and create a unique user experience for their customers. In addition, machine learning even improved the processing speed and accuracy of the processes even more through programmed algorithms. (*The Impact of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Insurance Sector*, 2020)

Besides the technologies in the insurance sector, there were also some general developments. One of these developments is the rise of more tailored insurance products. Everyone is different and thus needs a different insurance policy. That is why insurance companies have been offering more tailored insurance products throughout the years. The wide variety of options provide each customer

with a personal-fit insurance policy which they need. (Barndt, 2018)

Next to that, price comparison websites also made an impact on the insurance sector. The Decision Technology company in England stated in a paper of 2016 that the top three of price comparison websites account for approximately 80% of total sales in the insurance market. Insurance companies first felt threatened by these websites, but most of them managed to stay in business by offering better products and services. (*How to win the pricing game*, 2017)

ANALYSIS

IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing

First and foremost, according to the Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD, 2017) the governance structure of insurance companies “should have an appropriate allocation of oversight and administrative responsibilities, stipulate and delineate clearly the duties, responsibilities and qualifications of persons having responsibilities, and protect the rights of shareholders (or member-policyholders) and the interests of policyholders.”

Especially in times of sudden disruption it is of high importance to have a solid IT Governance practice in place to overcome challenges like business continuity, exchange of confidential information, & foreseeing in hardware, VPN, collaboration tools. Specific to COVID-19, considering on-site claims is challenging due to the danger of getting infected. All these challenges put pressure on growth and profitability prospects of insurance companies. (G. Shaw, 2020)

According to van Grembergen & de Haes (2008) cost reduction became an important concern for executives in the insurance industry. They show that up to 85% of IT budgets is allocated to ensure the continuity of the current level of service. Other IT Governance concerns are aligning the business strategy with the IT strategy. Typically, to achieve these goals several committees are instituted to guide the processes.

Based on three case studies on insurance companies conducted by van Grembergen & de Haes in 2008 the IT Governance framework (generic to the three insurance companies) as depicted in appendix I was created. With division between input rights (O) and decision rights (X).

Ernst & Young’s (EY) report on digital transformation opportunities show that big data analytics and machine learning can bring significant value in the field of cost reduction, customer experience enhancement, speed to market, sales productivity, underwriting efficiency, and claims efficiency. (EY, 2017) So the framework doesn’t necessarily need to change, because the focal point is still cost reduction. However, there are some issues that need to be addressed and re-evaluated due to the COVID-19 outbreak. For instance, Shaw argues that in order to overcome the disruption challenges insurance companies (but also organisations in general) need to establish cross-functional teams to coordinate an organisation’s response to crisis, set new safety protocols, and create abilities to respond quickly to the ever evolving environment. With specifics to machine learning models and business decisions resulting from these models, McKinsey argues that the first point of action is to reassess which machine learning models are actually required in order to ensure business continuity (McKinsey, 2020).

The graph in appendix II visualizes the impact COVID-19 has on model stability. As can be seen, machine learning models are of high importance for the insurance industry. Additionally, the instability of these models is equally high. Implications for the governance of these artifacts is thus that they need to be reassessed periodically. Regardless of whether there has been an infectious outbreak.

Another important note given in the report is that for future development of machine learning models, risk should be taken into account from the first day of building the models. This is backed up by another research report published by McKinsey: derisking AI by design, which speaks to the importance of the establishment of diverse teams, ethics training sessions, and risk metrics to use. Moreover, the report stresses creating a culture where an eye is kept open for varying risks that may influence the model output accuracy and reliability. Examples of risks to keep an eye open for are: changes in law and regulations, and policies, as well as evolving social trends.

Business Process Integration

The digital transformation brought on by the COVID-19 outbreak introduced changes in the processes of the organizations operating in the insurance sector. These changes can be due to regulatory changes or the adoption of new technologies. For the organizations it is important to look at the impact of these changes on the key

processes and how to face the challenges that these changes have brought about. Besides that it is interesting to see if the organizations in the insurance sector are able to adapt their products and services fast enough to the rapidly changing environment and if due these changes new opportunities will possibly arise.

At first due regulatory changes more employees are working remotely from home. Organizations should review the impact this remote working has on the effectiveness of delivering services to the customers. If the impact is positive insurance organizations have to determine whether the adoption of remote working and the new working practices can be the new norm as it provides the opportunity to weather future disruptive events and reduces fixed costs such as offices. Furthermore there are signs that due the COVID-19 situation the customer value will begin to change. Access to virtual healthcare and the opportunity to purchase policies and processes claims online will be a top priority for selecting insurers. Thereby insurers will bring more value to their customers with more personalized policies and offerings. To tailor these policies to the wishes of the customers, the insurance companies need more data from their customers and due the pandemic customers are more willing to share their personal data. The relationship between the insurance companies and the customers will make a shift towards a more symbiotic relationship on data exchange which thus leads to the creation of more individualized products. (Boffey, Fisher, McCorry, Pigg & Thomas, 2020) As part of these changes regarding the policies the insurance companies offer, COVID-19 will lead to the introduction of pandemic risk exclusion in new contracts with for example a payout being triggered once a certain number of cases have been registered in the specific area where the customer lives. Besides that in the future there will be a higher demand for health and life insurances than in the past. (Boffey et. al, 2020) For insurance companies this development means that they need to review their channel strategy approaches in order to serve this demand.

The evolution of the COVID-19 crisis forced insurance companies to adopt new digital operating models to increase flexibility. Although the digital transformation in the insurance industry had already started before the pandemic, Braun (2020) states that the pandemic has accelerated this development and can be seen as a catalysator. An example of the adoption of a new technology to improve the service delivery is the introduction of digital signatures. Due to the crisis, insurance companies expect a significant increase in young

people taking out insurance. (Vector ITC, 2020) The idea is to speed up the process welcoming new customers without the need for a physical signature which will improve the customer experience and contribute to the fact that the customers want to arrange their insurance activities online. In addition, one of the consequences of the COVID-19 crisis in the context of the adoption of new technologies has been the increase in online communication via video calling. According to Boffey et. al, (2020) insurance companies can take advantage of this transition by selling insurance products through the 'digital first' approach. This approach starts with a video call before moving the sale to other channels to complete which could lead to a reduction in distribution costs for the insurer and will increase access to personalized advice for the customer.

According to Vector ITC (2020) there are some main trends that have come to the insurance industry and have been strengthened as the result of COVID-19 affecting several key processes of many insurance companies. One of these key processes that was affected by the changes due COVID-19 is the claim handling process. Although the overall volume of claims may be reduced corresponding to a lower level of economic activity and customers staying at home, crises in general often trigger fraudulent and exaggerated claims. In order to detect these false claims, insurance companies need robust processes that can handle the increase in false claims. According to Deloitte (2020) advanced data analytics can be used to identify fraudulent behaviour. In addition to using advanced data analytics to identify fraudulent behaviour, insurers are examining robotic process automation and other methods to speed up manual claims processing where required. Finally, on site claims investigations have been hindered with reduced mobility due to the safety measures and lockdowns in several countries. This situation offers the opportunity to further implement the use of drones in claim investigations due to the fact that the use of drones makes remote claim investigations possible. In the two diagrams below a visual representation of how these developments affect the claim handling process as the result of the COVID-19 pandemic.

In conclusion, although the digital transformation had already started in the insurance sector, the COVID-19 crisis accelerated this development and will create new opportunities to improve both the customer value and the key processes of companies in the insurance sector.

Cybersecurity

Cyber risks have become a more common threat for several sectors in recent years. The digital transformation, the increasing use of big data and an increasing number of cyber attacks have also been influencing the insurance sector. Insurance companies are interesting targets for cyber criminals, because they possess a lot of data with confidential policyholders information. Although new technologies also offer a lot of advantages for the insurance sector, they need to see the risks and the consequences of these risks as well. Since cyber criminals become smarter and invent new sorts of cyber attacks to steal personally identifiable information from policyholders.

Following the European Insurance and Occupational Pension Authority the most common cyber incidents which affected the insurance sector in recent years were phishing mail, malware infection, denial of service (DDoS) attacks and data exfiltration. Hereby the biggest consequences were business interruption and material costs for policyholders and third parties. (EIOPA, 2019)

Covid-19 has impacted the insurance sector in many ways, resulting in a digital transformation that comes with various cybersecurity risks. In this section the cybersecurity risks that are related to the insurance sector will be described and analyzed. To rank these risks a risk matrix will be used and control measures will be described to reduce the impact and likelihood of the risks. (Refsfal et al., 2015)

1. Inside threats: Employees using their own devices and infrastructure

Due to Covid-19 more employees are working remotely from home. Organizations need to recognize that despite policies are in place, IT workarounds and business communication will likely occur on personal devices. Large scale remote work has resulted in less strict rules, concerning certain devices including personal laptops, printers and smartphones. Using a personal device for working remotely could lead to several cybersecurity risks. (AON, 2020)

First, it is important to understand why people are using their own devices instead of devices from their organization. In the ideal situation, devices are entirely

separated for corporate purposes and personal use. However, in reality, most organizations that did not follow a policy of issuing employees separate corporate devices prior to the coronavirus outbreak are highly unlikely to incur the costs of doing it now. (AON, 2020). This leads to the fact that employees are using personal devices for work if corporate devices are unavailable.

Now the reason why employees are using personal devices for corporate work is clear, the next step is to identify the associated risks of working from home:

A. Risk of data leakage between family members

As a result of using personal devices for work, there is an increased risk of data leakage if personal devices are shared between family members. The more family members are using the same device, the higher the probability that classified company data is exposed.

B. Risk of data leakage using unsafe networks

When family members are using a personal device while connected to an insecure network, the higher the probability of a data leakage occurring. Using the Wifi-network from home without a VPN connection will increase the chance of a possible data leakage. In The Netherlands stable power supply and fast internet connection is widely accessible, but in countries like Nigeria this is a luxury. Employees might work from public spaces to utilise power and free internet facilities. This behaviour may inadvertently expose confidential information. (Deloitte, 2020)

C. Risk of employees stealing companies intel

When employees are using their own personal devices at home, it is difficult to monitor which files are transferred to USB-sticks. This

created the risk of an employee transferring internal company information from the cloud to it's personal device, which shouldn't be a problem. But because it is difficult to monitor if these files aren't being copied to a USB-stick.

2. Channel overload of the VPN. Too many people using the network, which causes a failure.

One of the challenges insurance companies are facing is the risk over channel overload. (KPMG, 2020) This risk is due to the fact that many employees are working remotely from home because of Covid-19.

Many companies use VPNs dependent on traffic over the public internet, an unreliable transport which can develop problems as connections are made from different parts of the world. This translates into slowdowns and reduced quality of service overall. VPN's are designed to be used by a subgroup of employees. VPN's are not intended to be used by entire companies all at once. (Bukspan, 2020)

VPN accounts are licensed by a company, which means adding chunks of users is going to experience an increase in costs and time to set up and inform new users. The risk of doing so is that the internet traffic will be slower than before because the VPN becomes overloaded from spikes in traffic. On the other hand, not adding users to the VPN network will make employees more vulnerable for cyber attacks when transmitting data.

3. The insurance sector outsources more to other companies

To provide policyholders an extra service and more convenience, insurance companies use more digital channels where customers can see an overview of their current insurance portfolio, sign up for new insurance policies, change their current policy or where they can find information about how to reduce their security risks. Insurers use integrated platforms such as agency portals, web platforms, mobile apps and online policy

applications to provide these services to their customers. (Deloitte, 2020)

Insurance companies do provide an extra service for their customer and make the process easier by outsourcing a part of the business process to outsourcing providers. But on the other hand they lose control over a part of their assets, which brings more security risks. (EY, 2017)

4. Leaking of claims → private information

More insurance claims have been made electronically due to the Coronavirus. This brings less health risks, because people are not in contact with each other. But on the other hand it gives more cyber security risks. An intrusion can lead to identity theft, loss of financial assets and unauthorized credit card uses. Besides, it will also damage the insurers reputation. (Bazqandi & Golestan, 2015)

5. External threats

Insurance companies become more vulnerable to cyber attacks because of their increasing big data systems which include a large amount of personally identifiable information of their policyholders. Data security risks could be caused by technical errors and errors in external links to the systems. Technical errors consist of information leaks, information loss or incompatibility of the data systems. Besides, there are many possible cyber attacks which could lead to a data safety risk. (International Association of Insurance Supervisors, 2002)

The European Insurance and Occupational Pensions Authority has given a list of the most common cyber incidents which affected the insurance sector. The two most common cyber incidents are phishing mail and malware infection. (EIOPA, 2019)

A. Phishing mail

The most frequently used cyber attack by hackers is sending a phishing mail. Hereby, they send an email to a customer of a company where they will be

directed to a website when clicking on a link. On this website they will be asked to log-in to their account or update personal information such as credit card details, social security numbers, bank account numbers or passwords. When an insurance company loses their confidential data to people who are not authorized to have access to it, it could lead to breaches in the privacy of customers and employees. (EIOPA, 2019)

B. Malware infection

A malware infection (ransomware) is a type of malicious software which intends to damage a computer, steal private data and spy on a computer without consent of the user. The attacker mostly threatens to publish the data which they captured, or they block the access to their data till a ransom is being paid. (EIOPA, 2019)

Security risk scores

Risk	Impact	Probability	Score (impact*probability)
1a	3	1	3
1b	3	2	6
1c	4	4	16
2	5	2	10
3	5	1	5
4	4	1	4
5a	4	3	12
5b	5	2	10

Impact	Critical (5)	Risk analysis				
		Major (4)	1C	5A	2, 5B	3
Moderate (3)				1B	3A	
Minor (2)						
Insignificant (1)						
		Highly Probable (5)	Probable (4)	Possible (3)	Unlikely (2)	Rare (1)
		Probability				

The risk analysis matrix indicates which risks are more likely to happen and have the most impact combined. Measures that should be taken are the ones that reduce the highest scored risks or measures that reduce multiple risks at once.

Motivation for matrix input

Risk 1A: Risk of data leakage between family members

The impact of data leakage between family members is considered medium. The reason being is it depends on the function of the employee whose device has been shared with a family member. If the employee has a function with sensitive intel, the impact will be higher than with an employee that is working without sensitive intel. The probability of a data leakage between family members is rare because nowadays most people have their own personal devices.

Risk 1B: Risk of data leakage using unsafe networks

The impact of data leakage using unsafe networks is considered medium because if an employee would use an unsafe network and company data would be compromised, the impact depends on the type of data. If the data is sensitive, the impact will be high. If the data isn't sensitive, the impact will be low. The probability of using an unsafe network would be considered possible, at airports for example, but using an unsafe network (without VPN) doesn't mean that every time a data leakage has to happen. So for that reason the probability is estimated unlikely.

Risk 1C: Risk of employees stealing companies intel

The impact of employees stealing companies intel is estimated to be high. If an employee attempts to steal data from his company, most likely the employee will use this intel for his/hers own benefits. The employee must have an incentive to do so. If an employee steals company data to sell to

a competitor, the impact would be high because a competitor could use this information to stay ahead. Normally, the probability of an employee stealing companies intel wouldn't be considered as high. But nowadays when people are working from home, it is more difficult to monitor if an employee is stealing data from the company. Because of this lack of control, the probability is estimated to be higher than normal.

Risk 2: Channel overload of the VPN. Too many people using the network, which causes a failure.

The impact of too many people using the VPN which could cause a failure is estimated to be very high. If the VPN breaks down, operations that are sensitive and thus need an VPN, are going to be delayed. Otherwise the transmitted data is no longer secured by an VPN. The impact would be very high if vital corporations processes are delayed for an unknown period of time. Since COVID-19 is known since March, the assumption is made that a lot of organizations now have enough capacity for their employees to use a VPN server. That is the reason why the probability is to be estimated unlikely.

Risk 3: The insurance sector outsources more to other companies

An outsourcing company could sell the data to third parties, misuse the data or there could be a data breach. The impact of losing this data could have a big impact on the policyholder and on the insurance company. Outsourcing companies most of the time have all the possible data at their disposal, so it can cause a great impact. The probability of this happening is actually rare, because there are a lot of terms and conditions stated in the contracts which prevent these vulnerabilities.

Risk 4: Leaking of claims

The impact of a leakage of an electronic claim is high, because the personal identifiable information from customers are included in the contract. When hackers get access to a claim, they can sell the customers' data to other companies or misuse it against the customers. We do not see it as a very high impact, because it is about one single claim and not about all the available data. The probability of a leakage is rare, since the claims are well secured by the systems of the insurance companies.

Risk 5A: Risk of a data leakage due to phishing mail

The impact of a leakage of personal data depends on the kind of data which is being stolen. When someone fills in all their personal information, they could lose some money. But when company passwords are being stolen, attackers have access

to all the information they need. That is why we chose to put this risk in the fourth impact scale. The probability is rated as possible, because it is the most frequently used cyber incident which affected insurance companies. (EIOPA, 2019)

Risk 5B: Risk of a malware infection (ransomware)

The impact of a malware infection is very high. It could cause several consequences, such as a business interruption, material costs for policyholders and third parties, data destruction and a confidentiality breach. The effect of the attack depends on what the attacker demands. The probability that this incident occurs is unlikely. A malware infection could be activated when clicking on an unreliable link, when downloading an app, or through a mail or a text message. Employees in insurance companies are getting warned for these kinds of intruders, but of course there will always be a possibility that someone clicks on a wrong link.

Measures

1. Measures that should be taken to the four internal threats

In these unprecedented times of covid-19, organizations need to assure that they narrow their cyber risk exposure without decreasing their operational functionality. Security and functionality are closely entangled, which means if one were to take on an uneven weight over the other, there wouldn't be an even balance between them. To address the previous discussed cybersecurity risks, the following measures should be taken. These measures will reduce the risk of a cybersecurity breach.

- A. Create and implement a policy for employees that they should use a laptop from their organization if they need to work from home. If this solution isn't possible, perform security testing on systems from personal devices that employees are using for their work. In addition a policy should be made by the organization on how employees should use their laptop when they are performing work on their personal devices. For example if it is allowed to use their personal laptop for work when this laptop is shared with other family members. (Safaa, 2017)
- B. Ensure a high level of employee education. This means that people should be aware of risks that are associated with using

personal devices and they fully understand the relevant policies. The assumption is that if employees are fully aware of security risks, the likelihood increases that they install antivirus software and VPN's despite the lack of company oversight.

- C. Invest time into researching systems related to Mobile Device Management that could be successfully deployed onto a wide range of personal devices. These systems should be used to alleviate the pressure on IT administrators to monitor, secure and enforce policies on employee endpoints. This solution helps to monitor what employees are doing with company data on their personal devices. The employees will only be monitored when they use high sensitive company data or when they work with confidential policyholder information. (AON, 2020)

2. Measures that should be taken to avoid channel overload of the VPN

Insurance companies should renew their partnership with their Virtual Private Network provider in case they haven't done so already. They should inform how many users their VPN-plan can handle at once. If this isn't sufficient the insurance company should research what options are available to be able to scale up the amount of VPN users. But first, they should map out how many employees need an VPN for their work. In the meantime it is important to create a policy of who has the priority of using the VPN to guarantee that vital processes aren't disrupted.

Another solution would be to simplify the workflow. This means that employees wouldn't use the VPN all day, but instead do all the assignments for their work at one time slot of the day. At that specific time slot the VPN would be used. In this case, the amount of time using the VPN is reduced from all day long to specific time slots, which will improve the stability of the VPN.

3. Measures that should be taken to make outsourcing safer

Insurance companies need to create strict terms and conditions when outsourcing. Insurers can use the 'model contract for outsourcing' made by the European Commission to conform to these standards. The model contract for outsourcing contains subjects about conflict of interest, confidentiality and corruption in the performance of the contract. In addition, other extra measures

could be taken as well to prevent data leakage or misuse of information by outsourcing companies. (RBC Nederland, 2016)

4. Measures that should be taken to avoid leaking of electronic claims

Insurance companies can not ward off all the possibilities of leaking claims. But they can inform customers and train employees to create awareness about how to use the claims and where to store them. Training and informing customers and employees will reduce the risks of a leakage. Besides, insurance companies need to implement a comprehensive risk management and IT security system to largely prevent those risks from occurring. (*Information Security Breach in The Insurance Industry*, 2017)

5. Measures that should be taken to reduce external threats

Cyber security risks cannot be fully precluded, because cyber attackers will always invent new sorts of attacks. But on the other hand there are measures that could be taken to avoid a large extent of these attacks. One of these measures is to secure the hardware with password protection and with 2-way authentication. A second measure could be to protect the physical hardware, if someone can reach the actual hardware, it is easy for them to steal the data. A third possibility is to encrypt the data so no one can reach it. A fourth measure is the use of anti-malware solutions and firewalls, which will isolate each local area network from the rest of the systems. Finally, it is always good to back-up the data. When a hacker does succeed in stealing companies data, companies will always have the possibility to continue their work with the backed up data they still possess. (Goud, 2020)

- A. The paper of Gupta et al. (2016) states that there are two main measures to prevent phishing attacks from occurring. The first measure is to educate the users about several kinds of phishing attacks and prevention techniques. The second measure is the software-based defense approach, which include network level protection, authentication mechanisms, client side tools and server tools. These mechanisms and tools mention when a website or link is unsafe or sent by an unvalid path. (Gupta et al., 2017)
- B. The key measure against malware also starts with creating awareness of

employees, management and customers. Insurers need to educate their employees and inform their current and potential customers on how to be safe and secure online. Moreover, companies should take preventive measures such as frequently backing up their data and hardening their systems from different layers. (Luo & Liao, 2007)

Resilience

Resilience could be defined as 'the capacity of an enterprise to survive, adapt and grow in the face of turbulent change'. To be resilient, insurance companies need to find an equilibrium between their vulnerabilities and their capabilities. An increase of vulnerabilities could lead to more risks, with the result that companies need to improve their capabilities to reduce those risks. On the contrary, companies should not invest too much in improving their capabilities because it could lead to sunk costs. (Fiksel et al., 2015)

Due to the COVID-19 outbreak, millions of people are sitting at home. Insurance companies that did not catch up with the development of digital transformations in the fields of service, sales, distribution and claims could see the virus as a big threat. However, insurers that were investing in digital transformation now see the advantages of it. It is important to closely inform the insurance policyholders in times of a crisis situation, and the best way to do that is via digital channels.

The most important thing in terms of resilience at the beginning of a crisis situation is to act fast. Companies need to go for a pragmatic and quick solution instead of the perfect solution. Insurers need to adapt digital ways of working, closely inform their customers and employees with valuable information about new ways of working and how to secure them and search for innovations in new products, services and distribution. This way they will subsist and be better prepared for the future ahead. (Acharya et al., 2020)

Conclusion

Although insurance companies have already taken some steps to reduce cybersecurity risks, COVID-19 sped up the need to improve and add new measures to reduce cyber security risks. As this research uncovered, the digital transformation is still going on which enhances opportunities to abuse the systems of insurance companies. While more people are working from home, this increases

the need to take security measures even more. If the suggested measures are implemented, the impact and likelihood of a cyber security risk happening will be reduced.

DISCUSSION

It is believed that big data allows insurers to be able to see the big picture by supporting faster and deeper understanding of risk exposure. Being able to properly incorporate data from internal and external sources, monitoring disruptive events, pandemics and infection rates is enabling insurers to compute adequate and more accurate premium rates for their customers. We also believe that COVID 19 was a catalizator of deeper understanding and development of Big Data analytics in the Insurance Industry.

DISCUSSION ON BUSINESS PROCESS INTEGRATION

Due to COVID-19 events, the insurance industry needs to adapt and create new digital operating models. This research supports the claim that pandemic has indeed accelerated development of digital transformation. It has already started a long time ago, COVID -19 is only a catalizator. Do we need new more personalized company policies, new sets of standards, digital signatures, new digital operating models are just a few adjustments built on big data analytics in order to improve business process integration during disruptive events like pandemic? There is still lots to investigate in this field.

DISCUSSION ON IT GOVERNANCE AND STRATEGIC SOURCING

Insurers should properly plan training and preparing staff in terms of hardware and software to work not only remotely but also under social distancing regulations since possibly a pandemic situation will not change any soon. This could potentially be a period of productive planning, training and outreach to stakeholder groups at remote distances (Babuna, 2020).

As mentioned in the previous part of this research, cost reduction became an important concern next to aligning the business strategy with IT strategy. Insurance firms need to establish cross-functional teams in order to be able to coordinate their response to the crisis. Moreover, machine learning is crucial to assure continuity of the process.

Lastly, what is most important, insurers should establish a well-designed risk management team. A

team that is ready to take action if disruption is taking place, and without excuses.

DISCUSSION ON CYBERSECURITY

The number of malicious attacks and cyber-crimes has definitely increased during the COVID-19 crisis. We can observe in media continuous reports about various organizations falling victim to cybercrime. While most of our lives moved online we became more interesting prey. Cyber-criminals have exposed and exploited network weak spots resulting from remote work environments. Will many insurance companies fail to provide complete protection (for work-at-home employees)? The risk of their data breach, network shutdowns, network interruptions and malicious malware is higher since we work more online and lots of employees were not properly prepared. Phishing, smishing (SMS phishing) and vishing (voice phishing) attacks are all on the rise. Our tendency to click on infected emails has increased as a result of us being online more than ever. Moreover, remote work arrangements will remain with us for some time. Should then Insurance companies review their cybersecurity programs and make modifications as necessary to cover the associated risks and defeat potential risks?

How to do that? Big Data Analytics. Already 35 years ago, Robert Waterman observed in *In Search of Excellence* that companies are “data rich and information poor”, little has changed. Hence, the DRIP (Data Rich, Information Poor) status must change as the insurance industry enters into the new decade. COVID-19 pressures even greater. The amount of public and private data that insurers have access to can be and definitely should be leveraged above the insurance companies that fall behind on digital transformation in order to gain sustainable competitive advantage.

A RESEARCH AGENDA

Further research is needed. We did not take into consideration the extent of an advantage and disadvantage of organizations more and less digitally transformed. Moreover, quantifying and managing loss due to pandemics by insurers is crucial in order to be able to profit from Big Data analytics. Subjects like false claims, new premiums and other enormous economic costs should be investigated. What is more, we focused only on risks related to employees working from home, but we believe there is a lot to investigate regarding customers/clients. Those issues and many others should be grappled with by academics for a long time to come.

CONCLUSIONS

Risks do not spread in isolation, their speed and impact are amplified because they are interlinked, associated and connected. This trend will not reverse, rather it will intensify and sustain, that is why the insurance industry needs to adapt. Already now, we fear the effects and impact of current pandemic on business continuity. Therefore, as the world continues to face greater and different levels of risk, big data analytics is crucial in order to help insurers gain understanding and more insight on how to deal with disruptive events like pandemic and use it to its advantage. It is crucial to keep on developing understanding of data in real time on emerging risks.

The digital transformation brought on by the COVID-19 outbreak introduced changes in the processes of the organizations operating in the insurance sector. Although the digital transformation had already started in the insurance sector, the COVID-19 crisis accelerated this development. As mentioned in this article before, there are signs that due to the COVID-19 situation the customer value will begin to change which offers various opportunities for improvement in the future. In addition, the change caused by the pandemic also had an impact on the key processes of insurance companies. One of these processes that this article had focused on is the claim handling process, in which two activity diagrams have been used to visually represent how changes caused by the pandemic impact the various steps in this particular process.

As described in the above section on ITG, the framework does need no change. However, the COVID-19 outbreak did alert insurance companies and machine learning developers that there are always risks you have to consider. And considering risks starts at the beginning of creation, whether it is machine learning or civil engineering. Nonetheless, even if consideration is taken into account from the starting point, additional measures have to be taken to enable resilience when times come. A committee, an outbreak-management team, is to point forward in dealing with sudden disruption.

Moreover, although insurance companies have already taken some steps to reduce cybersecurity risks, COVID-19 sped up the need to improve and add new measures to reduce cyber security risks. As this research uncovered, the digital transformation

is still going on which enhances opportunities to abuse the systems of insurance companies. While more people are working from home, this increases the need to take security measures even more. If the suggested measures are implemented, the impact and likelihood of a cyber security risk happening will be reduced.

To sum up, digital transformation started a long time ago in the insurance industry, COVID-19 has only speeded it up, it was definitely a catalysator. Organizations should use this opportunity and work closely with Big Data in order to take advantage of such disruptive events like the current pandemic.

REFERENCES

- Acharya, A., Hamilton, D., Patiath, P., Surak, Z., Dienstag, G., & Ouwerkerk, J. v. (2020, April 29). *Insurance resilience in a rapidly changing coronavirus world*. Retrieved September 30, 2020, from <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/financial-services/our-insights/insurance-resilience-in-a-rapidly-changing-coronavirus-world>
- AFM. (2020). *Types of insurances*. Retrieved September 16, 2020, from <https://www.afm.nl/en/consumenten/themas/producten/verzekering/soorten>
- AON. (2020). COVID-19 & Bring Your Own Device Policies – How To Mitigate Risk In The New Normal. COVID-19 & Bring Your Own Device Policies – How To Mitigate Risk In The New Normal
- Barndt, E. (2018, January 17). *A SECTOR UNDERGOING TRANSFORMATION – CHANGES IN INSURANCE COMPANIES' BUSINESS MODELS*. financial services.mazars.com. Retrieved September 20, 2020, from <https://financialservices.mazars.com/sector-undergoing-transformation-changes-insurance-companies-business-models/>
- Bazqandi, S., & Golestan, A. (2015). *Insured risk perception towards electronic insurance*. iaiest.com. Retrieved September 28, 2020, from <http://iaiest.com/data-cms/articles/20190924113305amIAJBM1510018.pdf>
- Boffety, G., Fisher, D., McCorry, M., Pigg, & Thomas, T. (2020). Covid-19: customer and digitization in insurance. <https://home.kpmg/xx/en/home/insights/2020/05/covid-19-customer-and-digitization-in-insurance.html>
- Braun, A. (2020) Rethinking Insurance: COVID-19 as a Catalyst for the Digital Transformation in the Insurance Sector. <https://intech.swiss/rethinking-insurance-covid-19-as-a-catalyst-for-the-digital-transformation-in-the-insurance-sector/>
- Bukszpan, D. (2020). Working remotely due to the coronavirus? This technology from your employer is key. <https://www.cnbc.com/2020/03/10/working-remotely-due-to-the-coronavirus-this-technology-is-key.html>
- Catlin, T., Johannes-Tobias, L., Björn, M., & Valentino, R. (2017, March 1). *Insurtech - the threat that inspires*. Retrieved September 17, 2020, from <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/financial-services/our-insights/insurtech-the-threat-that-inspires>
- CBS. (2017, December 8). *Verzekeraars; aantal verzekeringsmaatschappijen einde jaar 1999-2015*. Retrieved September 17, 2020, from <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/cijfers/detail/71276ned>
- Competition in the Dutch health insurance market*. (2016, February). acm.nl. Retrieved September 17, 2020, from https://www.acm.nl/sites/default/files/old_publication/publicaties/16129_competition-in-the-dutch-health-insurance-market.pdf
- Deloitte. (2020). COVID-19's Impact on Cybersecurity. <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/ng/Documents/risk/ng-COVID-19-Impact-on-Cybersecurity-24032020.pdf>
- Deloitte. (2020). Global Cyber Executive Briefing. <https://www2.deloitte.com/be/en/pages/risk/articles/insurance.html>
- Deloitte. (2020). *Global Cyber Executive Briefing*. www2.deloitte.com. Retrieved September 25, 2020, from <https://www2.deloitte.com/be/en/pages/risk/articles/insurance.html>
- Deloitte. (2020, April 19) Impact of COVID-19 on the Insurance Sector. https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/ie/Documents/FinancialServices/Impact_of_COVID-19_on_the_Insurance_Sector.pdf
- The Dutch insurance market 2017*. (2018, December 12). assets.kpmg. Retrieved September 17, 2020, from <https://assets.kpmg/content/dam/kpmg/nl/pdf/2018/sector/verzekeraars/the-dutch-insurance-market-2017.pdf>

- EIOPA. (2019). *CYBER RISK FOR INSURERS—CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES*. eiopa.europa.eu. Retrieved September 25, 2020, from https://www.eiopa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publications/reports/eiopa_cyber_risk_for_insurers_sept2019.pdf
- EY. (2017). *Cyber strategy for insurers*. www.eylaw.ca. Retrieved September 28, 2020, from [https://www.eylaw.ca/Publication/vwLUAssets/ey-cyber-strategy-for-insurers/\\$FILE/ey-cyber-strategy-for-insurers.pdf](https://www.eylaw.ca/Publication/vwLUAssets/ey-cyber-strategy-for-insurers/$FILE/ey-cyber-strategy-for-insurers.pdf)
- Fiksel, J., Croxton, K., Polyviou, M., & Pettit, T. (2015, November 3). *From Risk to Resilience: Learning to Deal With Disruption*. researchgate.net. Retrieved September 30, 2020, from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Timothy_Pettit/publication/283463392_From_Risk_to_Resilience_Learning_to_Deal_With_Disruption/links/5639267708aed5314d221c0b/From-Risk-to-Resilience-Learning-to-Deal-With-Disruption.pdf
- Goud, N. (2020). *Ways to prevent cyber attacks on your company*. cybersecurity-insiders.com. Retrieved September 30, 2020, from <https://www.cybersecurity-insiders.com/ways-to-prevent-cyber-attacks-on-your-company/>
- Grembergen, W. (2008). IT Governance in practice: six case studies. In S. Haes (Red.), *Implementing information technology governance* (pp. 125–236). IGI Publishing.
- Gupta, B., Tewari, A., Jain, A., & Agrawal, D. (2017). *Fighting against phishing attacks: state of the art and future challenges*. Retrieved September 30, 2020, from file:///C:/Users/Jarno/Downloads/Gupta2017_Article_FightingAgainstPhishingAttacks.pdf
- How to win the pricing game*. (2017). detech.co.uk. Retrieved September 20, 2020, from https://www.dectech.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/dectech_brief_pulling_rank.pdf
- Hida, E. (2018). Reimagining risk management to mitigate looming economic dangers and non financial risks. Deloitte Insights. Retrieved from https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/insights/us/articles/4222_Global-risk-management-survey/DI_global-risk-management-survey.pdf
- The Impact of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Insurance Sector*. (2020). oecd.org. Retrieved September 17, 2020, from <https://www.oecd.org/finance/Impact-Big-Data-AI-in-the-Insurance-Sector.pdf>
- Information Security Breach in The Insurance Industry*. (2017, April 5). cloudsecuretech.com. Retrieved September 28, 2020, from <https://www.cloudsecuretech.com/information-security-breach-in-the-insurance-industry/>
- International Association of Insurance Supervisors. (2002, October). *RISKS TO INSURERS POSED BY ELECTRONIC COMMERCE*. Retrieved September 28, 2020, from file:///C:/Users/Jarno/Downloads/Risks_to_Insurers_Posed_by_Electronic_Commerce_July_2003.pdf
- KPMG. (2020). Implications of COVID-19 on insurers' risk management and insurance steering for East Africa. https://home.kpmg/content/dam/kpmg/ke/pdf/covid-19/KPMG_EA_COVID_19_First_Assessment_for_Regional_Insurers-Webinar_Presentation.pdf
- Luo, X., & Liao, Q. (2007, September 19). *Awareness Education as the Key to Ransomware Prevention*. Retrieved September 30, 2020, from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/10658980701576412>
- McKinsey. (2019, april). *Confronting the risk of artificial intelligence*. <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/mckinsey-analytics/our-insights/confronting-the-risks-of-artificial-intelligence>
- McKinsey. (2020, augustus). *Derisking AI by design: how to build risk management into AI development*. <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/mckinsey-analytics/our-insights/derisking-ai-by-design-how-to-build-risk-management-into-ai-development>
- McKinsey. (2020b, september). *Leadership's role in fixing the analytics models that COVID-19 broke*. <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/mckinsey-analytics/our-insights/leaderships-role-in-fixing-the-analytics-models-that-covid-19-broke>

- Peters, T. J., & Waterman, R. H. (1982). *In search of excellence: Lessons from America's best-run companies*. New York: Harper & Row.
- RBC Nederland. (2016). GENERAL TERMS AND CONDITIONS FOR OUTSOURCING PERSONNEL AND LEASING/SELLING EQUIPMENT. <https://www.rbc-nederland.nl/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2018/09/2016-General-terms-and-conditions-for-outsourcing-personnel-and-leasing-selling-equipment-RBC-Special-1.pdf>
- Refsfal, A., Solhaug, B., & Stolen, K. (2015). *Cyber-risk Management* (Online edition ed.). Springer. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-23570-7_5
- Safaa, N. S. (2017). Motivation and opportunity based model to reduce information security insider threats in organisations. Motivation and opportunity based model to reduce information security insider threats in organisations
- Soar, J. (2015). *The changing face of the insurance industry*. Retrieved September 17, 2020, from [https://www.ey.com/Publication/vwLUAsets/ey-the-changing-face-of-the-insurance-industry/\\$FILE/ey-the-changing-face-of-the-insurance-industry.pdf](https://www.ey.com/Publication/vwLUAsets/ey-the-changing-face-of-the-insurance-industry/$FILE/ey-the-changing-face-of-the-insurance-industry.pdf)
- Vector ITC (18 August, 2020). The insurance industry prepares for a post-Covid scenario. <https://www.vectoritcgroup.com/en/tech-magazine-en/digital-transformation-en/the-insurance-industry-prepares-for-a-post-covid-scenario/>

APPENDIXES

Appendix I: IT Governance Matrix (based on three case studies within the insurance industry). An O denotes input rights, a X denotes decision rights.

Decision Archetype	IT Principles	IT Architecture
Business Monarchy		
IT Monarchy		
Feudal		O
Federal	X	
Duopoly (IT & Another group)	O	X
Anarchy		

Appendix II: McKinsey graph on Machine Learning model stability.

Impact of COVID-19 crisis on model stability, by

Appendix III: Activity diagrams insurance industry

